

Distributed Systems For Data Processing

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1 Introduction

A Distributed System¹ is a set of software and hardware resources called nodes that function independent of each other toward processing a common goal or problem statement. The complexity of a Distributed System is hidden to the end user making it to be seen a single independent entity.

Figure 1: Distributed Systems

The Characteristics of Distributed Systems are :

1. No Shared Clock
2. No Shared Memory
3. Concurrency
4. Heterogeneity And Loose Coupling
5. Distributed Systems are Dynamic
6. Built On Overlay Networks

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nH4qjmP2KEE>

1.1 Commonly Used Terms

1.1.1 Node

A Node is an independent Software/Hardware unit capable of running independently with its own processor or memory

1.1.2 Resource

A Resource is an asset like files,storage facilities,services,etc that can be accessed remotely over the Distributed system network

1.1.3 Distribution Transparency

Distribution transparency is the process in which the processes that take place in the distributed system is hidden from the end user. It includes information like

- Location of the servers/nodes
- Failure of nodes
- Migration and Replication of Nodes

1.1.4 Middle ware

Middle ware is the logical layer built over the nodes of the Distributed System to act as an interface between the nodes and the client side API connections . The functions of Middle ware are :

- Communication and Security services
- Handle failures

1.1.5 Concurrency

Concurrency is the ability of the distributed system to run multiple tasks simultaneously at a time.

1.2 Motives for using Distributed Systems

- Geographical Distribution Of Data
- Resource Sharing
- Data Replication
- Horizontal Scalability

1.3 Pros And Cons

1.3.1 Pros

- Reliability
- Scalability
- Fault Tolerance
- Increased Performance

1.3.2 Cons

- Hard to detect Failure
- Redundancy
- Inconsistency

2 Types Of Distributed Systems²

1. Circuit Breaker
2. CQRS (Command Query Responsibility Segregation)
3. Event Sourcing
4. Ambassador Pattern
5. Leader Election
6. Publisher Subscriber Model
7. Sharding

2.1 Circuit Breaker

Circuit Breaker³ System of the distributed systems consists of a circuit breaker mechanism where when any service is unavailable, the connection to the service is temporarily shutdown. This reduces Downtime on the network and thereby saves bandwidth. It consists of 3 modes of operation :

- Closed : When the Service is functioning properly
- Open : When the Service is malfunctioning
- Half-Closed : When the Service has just been open and the system allows only a few requests to the service. When it is properly functioning then it is completely closed

²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nH4qjmP2KEE>

³<https://medium.com/geekculture/design-patterns-for-microservices-circuit-breaker-pattern-276249ffab33>

Figure 2: Circuit Breaker

2.2 CQRS

CQRS (Command Query Responsibility Segregation)⁴ is a system of data retrieval from the database where there are 2 different systems each for data writing and data reading with both of them connected to a common database

Figure 3: CQRS System

⁴<https://martinfowler.com/bliki/CQRS.html>

2.3 Event Sourcing

In Event Sourcing⁵ the previous queries are stored in the system . The system state is then determined by completely rebuilding the system from the beginning . The system continuously takes snapshots at different time interval to save the stack memory.

Figure 4: Event Sourcing

2.4 Ambassador Pattern

In Ambassador Pattern⁶, the core service has an ambassador function which handles all communication and network protocols between the servers. It encapsulates all the network protocols from the core system allowing it to perform independently

Figure 5: Ambassador Pattern

⁵<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yFjzGRb8NOK>

⁶<https://distributedsystemsmadeeasy.medium.com/ambassador-pattern-architectural-pattern-2ae0516f62e5>

2.5 Leader Election

Leader Election ⁷ method is used in those services where the service provided is critical and must be fail proof. It is used in critical services like payment services, etc. Here multiple redundant services are deployed with one of the server elected to become a leader and others the followers. Algorithms like RAFT are used for this.

Figure 6: Leader Election

2.6 Publisher Subscriber Model

In this model ⁸, it consists of 2 computers (Publisher & Subscriber). The Publisher is the computer that sends messages over a connection called topic to the subscriber computer. A publisher may publish over multiple topics to different computers. The topics are application specific messages. The message sent via this method will come in order

⁷<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TzwiGTbUSHg>

⁸<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=algmP8MGeL4>

Figure 7: Publisher & Subscriber Model

2.7 Sharding

In Sharding⁹ the data from the database is broken down into smaller chunks of data which is then fed to multiple smaller databases. Advantages of Sharding Are :

- Vertical Scaling : Instead of deploying much expensive hardware in cloud, one can deploy multiple smaller hardware instances of databases in cloud
- Specialized Databases : Here various databases can be maintained for various specialized functions
- Replication : Sharding can be used for data replication activities

Figure 8: Database Sharding

⁹MongoDB Database Sharding Concepts

3 Other References

- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distributed_computing
- <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/what-is-a-distributed-system/>
- <https://www.freecodecamp.org/news/a-thorough-introduction-to-distributed-systems-3b91562c9b3c/>